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Excipients in iron medications as potential causes of side effects in pediatric population

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Iron, one of the basic microelements, is necessary for the normal functioning of biochemical processes. A vast variety of enzymes have iron in their composition such as hemoglobin, myoglobin, cytochrome, peroxidase, indicating that its surplus, and especially deficit, can lead to serious health problems¹. The most common form of iron deficiency in the organism is sideropenic anemia, which is manifested by various symptoms of fatigue, immunity and skin fading, while in children can cause slow growth and development². The pediatric population is the most vulnerable for anemia development, due to increased iron requirements. Medications for pediatric usage which contain iron as an active substance are considered in this paper. Type and safety of excipients used in the given formulations were observed. Data on selected medicines (n = 6) were obtained from the website of the Agency for Medicines and Medical Devices of Serbia; and the statements are extracted from Section 2 (Qualitative and Quantitative Composition) and Subsection 6.1 (List of Excipients)³.

Six excipients (parabens, ethanol, propylene glycol, sorbitol, saccharose, saccharin sodium) were detected, which may result in appearance of side effects. Use of excipients is based on the improvement of dosage form characteristics. Parabene is a preservative, ethanol and propylene glycol are co-solvent, and sorbitol, saccharose and saccharin sodium improve the organoleptic properties of the dosage form, and in this way increase children's compliance.

In preterm infants, the use of ethanol at a dose of 0.2-1.8 mL per week is safe. If a dose is calculated per kilogram of body weight, it is concluded that preterm infants are exposed to a dose of ethanol higher than permitted⁴. Propylene glycol intoxication may lead to gastrointestinal tract disorders. Considering the frequency of the occurrence of adverse effects of ethanol, as well as propylene glycol (1/3 of ethanol intoxication), attention should be paid to the dosing of drugs for pediatric populations. The maximum safe dose for sorbitol does not exist, but side effects such as diarrhea and malabsorbia^{5,6} have been reported. It is also not recommended to take medication containing sorbitol in fructose-intolerant individuals. Saccharin and sucrose can rely lead to urticaria. Parabens can cause allergic reactions (possibly delayed) as well as contact dermatitis⁷.

Comparing side effects of drugs contained in the summary of drug characteristics and undesirable effects of excipients, it has been concluded that the occurrence of allergic

reactions, urticaria and dermatitis are present in preparations 2, 3 and 4 containing parabens in their composition. All selected drugs 1-6 can cause gastrointestinal side effects due to the presence of iron as an active substance, which can be more common in drugs 1, 3, 4 due to the presence of propylene glycol.

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References

1. Rodrigues VC, Mendes BD, Gozzi A, Sandrini F, Santana RG, Matioli G. Deficiência de ferro, prevalência de anemia e fatores associados em crianças de creches públicas do oeste do Paraná, Brasil. *Rev Nutr* 2011;24:407-20.
2. World Health Organization (WHO). Growth Reference 5–19 Years. Geneva: WHO; 2007. [acessado 2015 Jul 15] Disponível em [http:// who.org.int/growthref/who.pdf](http://who.org.int/growthref/who.pdf). [2018 Oct 15]
3. Agencija za lekove i medicinska sredstva Srbije. Promet i potrošnja lekova za 2016. [Online]. Available from: <https://www.alims.gov.rs/ciril/files/2018/08/PPL2016.pdf>. [15.10.2018.]
4. Whittaker A, Currie A, Turner M, Field D, Mulla H, Pandya H. Toxic additives in medication for preterm infants. *Arch Dis Child - Fetal Neonat Ed* 2009;94:F236-40.
5. Committee on Nutrition American Academy of Pediatrics. The use and misuse of fruit juice in pediatrics. *Pediatrics* 2001;107:1210–13.
6. Duro D, et al. Association between infantile colic and carbohydrate malabsorption from fruit juices in infancy. *Pediatrics* 2002;109:797–805.
7. Rowe RC, Quinn ME, Sheskey PJ. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*, 6th ed., Pharmaceutical Press, London, 2009.